

Altitude determination

Harald Schröer

2015

Often we have the problem at known appearance angle α and known distance b to calculate the height h of an object (for example a tower, a building or a mountain). If b is very small compared with the earth's radius (planet's radius) r , we can use the simple formula $h = b \cdot \tan \alpha$.

Now we view the case that the distance b isn't small compared with r . Now we must take into consideration the spherical form of the planet. The sine law is valid:

$$\frac{r}{\sin(90^\circ - \alpha - \beta)} = \frac{r + h}{\sin(90^\circ + \alpha)}$$

With $\sin(90^\circ + \alpha) = \cos \alpha$ and $\sin(90^\circ - \alpha - \beta) = \cos(\alpha + \beta)$ we obtain:

$$h = \frac{r \cdot \cos \alpha}{\cos(\alpha + \beta)} - r$$

simplified:

$$h = r \cdot \left(\frac{\cos \alpha}{\cos(\alpha + \beta)} - 1 \right)$$

We don't know β but the distance b . The relation is:

$$\beta = \frac{b}{\pi r} \cdot 180^\circ$$

In circular measure we have got $\beta = \frac{b}{r}$. If α is in circular measure, then we get:

$$h = r \cdot \left(\frac{\cos \alpha}{\cos \left(\alpha + \frac{b}{r} \right)} - 1 \right)$$

In the case of α in degree:

$$h = r \cdot \left(\frac{\cos \alpha}{\cos \left(\alpha + \frac{b \cdot 180^\circ}{\pi r} \right)} - 1 \right)$$

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001